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Review Paper

Integrated Macro-Microscopic, Physicochemical and Phytochemical Profiling of *Abutilon Indicum* for Herbal Drug Standardization

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal herbs are frequently employed in health care delivery system, either alone or in conjunction with other medications. Medicinal herbs have potential therapeutic benefits and valuable sources of hither to unidentified compounds. It is Indian name is atibala: Ati is a meaning of "very" and sign that bala is meaning "powerfull" alludes to plants extremely potent qualities. A popular shrub in India ABUTILON INDICUM is a member of the (malvaceae) family. It has been rapidly and expanding in India, Australia, and Asia. Atibala is hairy under shrub with colour is golden yellow found in parts of India. In both Ayurvedic and Unani medicine, many plant parts, including leaf, flowers, seeds, roots, barks and fruits are traditionally utilized as medicines. It is microscopic section epidermis trichomes analysis. The plants are mostly used in Siddha treatment. To determine physicochemical evaluation. According to reports, *Abutilon indicum* possesses antioxidant and antimicrobial, hepatoprotective activity, mycosis infections, diuretic activity, anti-inflammatory and antiproliferative, diabetic activity, diarrhoea, immunomodulatory activity, wound healing, lipid lowering activity, Plasmodium malaria, anti-convulsion, anti-ulcer and anti-tumour. Pile issues are also treated using the leaf and flower are used to produce more seeds. Alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, glycosides, steroids, amino acid and phenolic substances have all been shown to be present in this plant. The goal of this review is to emphasize the humeral publications on ABUTILON INDICUM macroscopic, microscopic, ethnobotanical and traditional uses as well as its phytochemical and pharmacological properties.

INTRODUCTION

The people have utilized medicinal plants herb for their medicinal benefits and health benefits. The

health benefits plants used in medicines in naturally provided in therapeutic substances, and health issues used in medications in herbs or natural sources. The used of claims in these agents

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medications present in many seclusion. The *abutilon indicum* belongs to (malvaceae) family. The presently population for the administration of some health problems. The atibala is shrubs plants widely distributed in tropical and sub tropical countries in America, Africa, Sri lanka, Austrila and Asia. It is quite to common more in indiagrowings road sides and mountains before winter. The leafs was coloured founded to pedicellate or yellow colour, and orange yellow colour in flower , The fruits was divided into different mericarp, discoid segments and arranged in five petals, five sepals, five – twenty carpels in gynoeceium. Include seeds shaped to reniform in black to dark brown colour. The whole plant observed to covered in trichomes. The microscopically features (histological) characters epidermis part of the trichomes is formed of polygonal with anticlinal wall with stomata . Sclernchyma , parenchyma , cortex, endodermis, vascular system, pericycle, pith and physicochemical evaluation deterimined. The presecence of plant contains several pytochemicalconstuents such as a flavonoids , steroids,protein, phyto sterols, amino acid, alkaloids, terpoinds, proto alkaloids, glycosidis, tannins, triterpenes, saponins,phenolic and carbohydrates. The fibres obtained from the plant like atibala, abutilon polyandrum, abutilon asiaticum , abutilon grandiflorum and pannosum. It has been proved various biological activity and pharmacological activity to treat the various illness, antiinflammation, analgesic, pain killer, antipyretic, gastrointental disorder, liver damage, seizures or convulsion, hematuria (urinary tract infection in blood) antineoplastic(cancer), antioxidant, antimicrobial, antimycosis, antidiarrhea, anti hyperlipidermic,immunomodulatory, wound healing and plasmodium falciparum.

Abutilon indicum was mostly growing in road sides , waste area and mountain area (Tutti).

FIG 1: ABUTILON INDICUM PLANT

2.1. GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRUBATION:

In the sub - Himalayan and Other hills up to 1200 meteres, It is Indian Indian mallow [Atibala] as weed. It mostly shrub in Sub-tropical parts, Asia ,India, Austrila&Srilanka .

2.6. AYURVEDIC PROPERTIES:

Guna(properties) -Laghu,Snigdhd,Pichil

Rasa (Taste) -Madhur

Vipak(Metabolism)-Madhur

Virya (Potency) -Sheet

Prabhav (Impact) -Balya

2.7. VERNACULAR NAMES:

Tamil: PerumTutti, PaniyaraHutti, Thuthi

Bengal: Petari, Jhapi

Marathi: Mudra

Gujarathi: Khapat,dabali

Malayalam: Vellula

Arabian: MasthulGola

English: Country mallow

Hindi: Kanghi,Kakahi

Kannada: Tutti

Telugu: Tutturu Benda

2.8. BOTANICAL DISTRIBUTION:

Kingdom: Plantae-plants
SubKingdom: Tracheobionta-Vascular plants
Family: Malvaceae-mallow family
Genus: *Abutilon* Mill-Indian mallow
Class: Magnoliopsida-Dicotyledons
Sub class: Dilleniidae
Division: Magnoliopsida-dicotyledons
Order: Malvales
Species: *ABUTILON INDICUM* (L.) Sweet-Monke

3. PHARMACOGNOSTIC EVALUATION:

3.1. MICROSCOPICAL CHARACTERS:

The following features were visible in transverse section: the covering and glandular trichomes founded by lamina region, as well as upper epidermis. Trichoma was multicellular and uniseriate in nature. The stomata of anomocytic type that are found beneath in lower epidermis. Merophyll was made up of calcium oxalate crystals in palisade cells. Dorsal and ventral leaves and midrib are comparable. It is composed of densely packed collenchyma cells. 2-3 layer in upper parts and 3-4 lower parts of layers. Phloem cells and xylem make up vascular bundles.

3.3. POWDER MICROSCOPY:

The powder colour was determined by its morphological characteristics:

Emerald green, with a sweet to distinctive flavour and no smell. Identify pigment used present in calcium oxalate added ground powder phloroglucinol and conc. HCl staining made liquefied fibres. Glycerine allowed to debution covered globular trichomes.

4. ETHNICAL USES:

4.1. LEAVES:

Diabetes mellitus is one among the many ailments that the leaves have historically been used to cure.

Gonorrhoea, quick ulcer healing, bladder irritation, eye and mouth cleansing, toothaches, and sore gums are other conditions for which it is used.

4.2. FLOWER:

Men utilize the blooms to boost their semen production. Boils and ulcers are treated with flower paste.

4.3. ROOT:

Root is used as a diuretic and pulmonary sedative, and it can be used to treat hematuria.

It works well to treat leprosy as well.

4.4. BARK:

The bark is used as a diuretic for high urine production or complaints, an anthelmintic for worm infections, tape infections, lung conditions, and a sedative for fever.

4.5. SEEDS:

In India, seeds are used to treat fever, coughs, diabetes, dronchitis, and dysuria.

5. PHYSICO-CHEMICAL EXAMINATION:

More research has been done on the chemical composition of the leaves, roots, bark, flowers, and seeds of *Abutilon indicum* species. Alkanol, n-alkane mixture, leucine, histidine's hexoses, threonine, serine, and aspartic acid are the main physicochemical components present throughout the entire plant. With the help of molecules that indicated the presence of these compounds, infrared, ultraviolet, and nuclear magnetic resonance techniques were used to identify them.

5.1. ALKALOIDS:

Compounds originating from plants with a basic nature having one or more nitrogen atoms in ring structure" are known as alkaloids. Alkaloids and

related chemicals, including hexones, thronine, tropane, indole, pseudo alkaloids, peroine bases, n-alkane, diterpenes, and piperidine, are abundant in *Abutilon indicum*. The plant's leaves, roots, flowers, and seeds are the main locations for these substances. Vasicinone's bronchodilator qualities, which help increase forced expiratory volume (FEV1), are widely recognized.

5.2. FLAVONIODES:

The name "flavonoids" describes a vast class of water-soluble, biologically active plant compounds, such as flavones, which are mostly found in fruits, vegetables, and herbs and contain pigments with colors ranging from yellow to red to blue. Plant parts, seeds, and flowers of *Abutilon indicum* contain specific compounds such as quercetin 3-o-beta-glucopyranoside, apigenin-7-o-beta-glucopyranoside, 7-o-beta-glucopyranoside, and chrysaeriol 7-o-beta-glucopyranoside. Luteolin is known to have strong antioxidant and free radical scavenging properties as well as angiogenic-related compounds.

5.3. SAPONINS:

Natural plants called saponins are generated from triterpanes, which produce soap-like foams in water and surface active agents in amphiphilic glycosides. *Abutilon indicum* shows a high yield of around 30% in herbal sources, such as diosgenin and steroidal saponins, and has been detected in several compounds, such as plant parts in Indian mallow fruits, stems, and leaves. Diosgenin has been connected to antioxidants, gram-negative bacteria like *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas*, and hormone precursors.

5.4. TANNINS:

Plant extracts contain complex compounds called tannins, which react with animal proteins. They occur as combinations of

polyphenols and are exceedingly difficult to separate since they do not crystallize. Plant parts such as roots, stems, and leaves of *Abutilon indicum* contain substances such as hexahydroxy phenolic acid, flavanoids, catechins, flavan 3,4-diols, and ellagitannins.

5.5. GLYCOSIDES:

Glycosides are chemical compounds originating from plants or animals that release one or more sugar moieties when degraded by acids or enzymes. *Abutilon indicum* contains monosaccharide oligosaccharides, quercetin, glycone, aglycone, flavones, beta sitosterols, caffeine acids, glutamine, and histidine in all parts of the plant, including the roots, leaves, and flowers. Valine, tyrosine, alanine, saponins, leucine, and its histidine are cathartic stabilizers.

5.5. STEROIDS:

The hypocholesterolemic action of s-squalene 2,3 epoxide produces steroids, a large family of naturally occurring products. *Abutilon indicum* was acquired by K.N. Chopra using pyrochemical study of leaf extract. The non-drying oil extracted from *Abutilon indicum* contains compounds such as myristic, beta sitosterol, alpha amyrin, beta amyrin, palmitic, and lauric, capric, and special compounds like sitosterol, amyrin, and C17 chemical skeleton that were produced from non-sustainable sources and treat cardiac glycoside issues.

5.6. AMINO ACIDS:

Amino acids are substances that have an amino group, a carboxyl group, and a side chain unique to each amino acid. 8,9-methylene-heptadec-8-enoic (malvalic acid), 9,10-methylene octadec-9-enoic (sterculic acid), and cis-12,13-epoxyoleic (verndic acid) acid are produced by Chakraborty GS, Ghorpade PM, which resembles sections of

abutilon indicum in seeds. high concentrations of palmitic acid, steric acids, and unsaturated acids. Raffinose was the main sugar found in seeds. Serine, glutamine, lysine, methionine, isoleucine, alanine, proline, tyrosine, phenylalanine, leucine, asporphine, histidine, and valine are among the amino acids found in seed proteins.

5.7. PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS:

The strain was effectively isolated to yield 20,23-dimethylcholesta 6,22 dien 3beta-ol. effectively extract within a strain. Caffeine acid, p-coumaric acid, gallic acid, p-beta-d-glycosylox benzoic acids, vanilic acids, ferulic acids, and 4-hydroxybenzine are among the chemical constituents found in Vedarijaya T, a 50% ethanol extract that contains fannins. Plants are used to treat astrigentla inflammation.

6. PHYSICO-CHEMICAL EVALUATION:

6.1. Foreign Matter Determination Process:

Foreign matter refers to any unwanted substances such as soil, sand, stones, insects, or other plant parts mixed with the crude drug. It is used to determine the purity of plant material, detect adulteration, and ensure the herbal drug is clean and safe for further processing.

METHOD:

Take roughly 100 g of Abutilon indicum powder that has been air-dried. On a sanitized tray, spread the sample thinly. Use a magnifying lens (6x) or the unaided eye to examine. Eliminate extraneous objects including sand, stones, insects, and other plant pieces. Accurately weigh the foreign material.

FORMULA:

$$\% \text{Foreign matter} = \frac{\text{weight of foreign matter}}{\text{weight of sample}} \times 100$$

6.2. Method for Calculating Loss on Drying (Moisture Content):

Moisture content is the amount of water or volatile components present in the plant material, measured by drying it to constant weight. It is used to assess the stability of the drug, prevent microbial growth or spoilage, and ensure the material remains suitable for long-term storage.

METHOD:

Place two to five grams of powdered medication in an evaporating dish that has been previously weighed. Put the dish in a 105°C hot air oven. After three hours of drying, chill in a desiccator. Weigh once more. Continue drying until the weight remains steady.

FORMULA:

$$\% \text{loss on drying} = \frac{\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{initial weight}} \times 100$$

6.3. Method for Determining Total Ash:

Ash value is the total amount of inorganic residue left after incinerating the plant drug. It is used to detect contamination with inorganic matter, evaluate purity, identify adulteration with sand or soil, and ensure the mineral content stays within acceptable limits.

METHOD:

Weigh two grams of powdered medication that has been air-dried precisely. Put in a silica crucible that has been lit and weighed. Heat the incinerator gradually to 450–600°C until all carbon has been eliminated. Weigh after cooling in a desiccator.

FORMULA:

$$\% \text{ Total ash} = \frac{\text{Weight of ash}}{\text{weight of sample}} \times 100$$

6.4. Acid-Insoluble Ash Determination Method:

Extractive value refers to the amount of active constituents extracted from the plant using different solvents like water or alcohol. It is used to estimate the presence of phytochemicals, select the best extraction solvent, and standardize the quality and potency of herbal drugs.

METHOD:

For five minutes, bring the whole ash and 25 milliliters of diluted hydrochloric acid to a boil. Use ash-free filter paper to filter. Use hot water to clean the residue. In a crucible, ignite the filter paper containing residue. Weigh and cool.

FORMULA:

$$\% \text{ Acid insoluble ash} = \frac{\text{weight of residue}}{\text{weight of sample}} \times 100$$

6.5 Method for Determining Water-Soluble Ash:

The pH of an extract indicates its acidity or alkalinity when dissolved in water. It is used to ensure chemical stability, determine compatibility with formulations, monitor microbial safety, and maintain proper storage conditions for herbal preparations.

METHOD:

For five minutes, bring 25 milliliters of distilled water to a boil with complete ash. Use ash-free filter paper to filter. Use hot water to wash. Light the insoluble substance on fire. Deduct this weight from the total amount of ash.

FORMULA:

$$\% \text{ Water soluble ash} = \frac{\text{Total ash} - \text{insoluble matter}}{\text{weight of sample}} \times 100$$

6.6. Method for Determining Alcohol-Soluble Extractive Value:

Powder flow properties describe how easily powdered plant material can move, pack, and compress, measured through parameters like angle of repose and bulk density. They are used to evaluate flowability for tablet/capsule preparation, ensure smooth processing, and optimize handling during manufacturing.

METHOD:

Weigh five grams of powdered medication that has been air-dried. For a full day, macerate 100 milliliters of 90% ethanol in a closed flask. During the first six hours, shake a lot. Quickly filter. In a dish covered with tar, evaporate 25 milliliters of the filtrate until it is completely dry. Weigh after drying at 105°C.

FORMULA:

$$\% \text{ Alcohol soluble extractive} = \frac{\text{Weight of extract}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

6.7. Method for Determining Water-Soluble Extractive Value:

The foaming index measures the ability of an aqueous extract to produce foam, indicating the presence of saponins. It is used to estimate saponin content, identify saponin-rich drugs, and support the standardization and quality evaluation of herbal materials.

METHOD:

Weigh five grams of powdered medication For a whole day, macerate with 100 milliliters of distilled water. Shake from time to time. 25 milliliters of filtrate should be filtered and evaporated. Dry to a consistent weight at 105°C.

FORMULA:

$$\% \text{ Water soluble extractive} = \frac{\text{Weight of extract}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

6.8. Method for Determining pH Value:

The pH of an extract indicates its acidity or alkalinity when dissolved in water. It is used to ensure chemical stability, determine compatibility with formulations, monitor microbial safety, and maintain proper storage conditions for herbal preparations.

METHOD:

Make aqueous solutions of the powdered medication at 1% and 10%. Use buffer solutions to calibrate the pH meter. At room temperature, measure the pH. Take note of the readings.

6.9. Crude Fiber Content Determination Process:

Fluorescence analysis involves observing the color changes of plant material under UV light after treatment with different reagents. It is used for identification and authentication of crude drugs, detecting adulteration, and establishing characteristic fluorescence fingerprints for quality control.

METHOD:

Weigh two grams of powdered defatted medication. For thirty minutes, bring 200 milliliters of 1.25% sulfuric acid to a boil. After filtering, use water to wash. For half an hour, boil

the residue in 200 milliliters of 1.25% sodium hydroxide. Filter, clean, dry, light, and weigh.

6.10. The Swelling Index Calculation Process:

The swelling index represents the increase in volume of plant material when soaked in water, reflecting the content of mucilage, gums, or pectins. It is used to evaluate mucilage-rich drugs, assess quality for demulcent or laxative use, and standardize formulations requiring swelling action.

METHOD:

Fill a 25 ml measuring cylinder with 1 g of powdered medication. Add up to 25 milliliters of distilled water. For one hour, give it a good shake every ten minutes. Let it stand for a full day. Calculate the final volume.

FORMULA:

$$\text{Swelling Index} = \frac{\text{final volume occupied by swollen drug (ml)} - \text{initial volume of drug (ml)}}{\text{weight of drug taken (g)}}$$

7. PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY:

7.1. ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITIES

Anti-microbial properties Escherichia coli and streptococcus pyogenes were among the microbial strains against anti-bacterial and activity was examined. The disc or diffusion method select these species. Ethanol and H₂O used to create in plant extracts. High sensitive than streptococcus pyogenes compared standard medication in chloramphenicol. The leaf, root, seed, and fruit extracts of Abutilon indicum do not significantly inhibit the following microorganisms: Candida albicans, Staphylococcus aureus, Salmonella, Enterococci, Shigella, K. pneumoniae, E. coli, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Aspergillus niger, Steptococcus

cerevisiae, *Micrococcus luteus*, and *Bacillus pumilus*. The lack of effectiveness against the strains mentioned above indicates that the antibacterial activity is deficient. demonstrate mycelial inhibition or blocking of *Absidiaramos* and *Aspergillusniger*

7.3. ANTI-FUNGAL ACTIVITY:

Rajalakshmi podma vaira vasundaram and colleagues have reported anti-mycotic activity of compounds *Abutilon indicum* (malvaceae). Exhibits strong anti-fungal activity against trichophyton. *ABUTILON INDICUM* leaf extracts in methanolic water, volatile compounds, and water extracts have anti-mycosis properties against *Trichophytonrobrum*. It is used to treat systemic fungal infections, dermatophyte infections in the skin and mucocautaneous candidiasis, nail problems, aspergillosis, and fungal infections (mycoses).

7.4. HEPATOPROTECTIVE:

Abutilon indicum's aqueous extract was examined for hepatoprotective properties against hepatotoxicities caused by paracetamol and carbon tetrachloride. The plant extract may have a hepatoprotective effect by interfering with the production of free radicals. Liver diseases are mostly caused by toxic chemicals, excessive alcohol consumption, infections, and autommunine disorders. All of these substances must be shielded from the liver.

7.5. ANTI- INFLAMATORY:

The anti-inflammatory and anti-proliferative activity of ethanolic leaf extracts of *abutilon indicum* chemo preservative agents been anti-inflammatory. The invesitegated the kalodharetal assessed in anti-proliferative and anti-inflammatory properties leaf in ethanolic extract preventive chemotherapy according to5-

lipoxygenase (5-lox)inhibition test. Anti-inflammatory medicines, such as Ibuprofen and naproxen, are used to treat rheumatoid arthritis, muscle strains, tooth or dental discomfort, rheumatoid arthritis, and carrageenan/formaldehyde-induced edema in animal models.

7.6. ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY:

Abutilon indicum is hypoglycemis effects in sertharan ethal. The oxidase peroxide method was used not discernide effect in hypoglycaemic $CHCL_3$ extract and petrol in leaves. Alcohol chemical compounds like beta cells and glycosides damaged pancreatic hormones. Leaves, roots, and stems are the primary plant sections that are investigated. It is primarily similar to metformir and sultonyiurea. Reduced blood sugar, increased insulin secretion, gastric diabetes (occurring during pregnancy), essential carbohydrate metabolism, decreased glucose levels, and immune-boosting action are all cured by plant parts.

7.7. ANTI-DIARRHOEAL ACTIVITY:

Abutilon indicum was extrat in plants in diarrhoeal activity in therphy of oral rehydration thearphy in mangementes of diarrhea treat loperamide and pepto-bismol in reduced diarrhea. Both castor oil-induced diarrhea and prostaglandin E2-induced diarrhea were significantly reduced by the methanolic and aqueous extracts. By preventing intestinal peristalsis, gastrointestinal motility, and PGE2-induced enteropooling, these extracts decreased diarrhea.

Leaves, roots, and plants are primarily responsible for this. In particular, prostaglandin was induced by castor oil and methanolic and aqueous extracts. Similar to loperamide and colloidal bismuth subsalisaliscylate, it is mostly used to treat

gastrointestinal disorders, diarrhea, stomach problems, and decreased stools.

7.8. ANTI-OXIDANT ACTIVITY:

The aqueous extract from level glucose absorption and stimulated sugar level secretion extract contains, tannin, alkaloids, saponins, glycosides in plant extract. Steam leaves are the most popular source. Methanolic and ethanolic extracts in particular. It reduces oxidative stress and neutralizes free radicals in oxidative stress.

7.9. IMMUNOMODULATORY ACTIVITY:

Heamagglutination antibody (HA) titre, delayed type hypersensitivity neutrophil, adhesion, clearance carbon test used by immunomodulatory activity leaf extracts. Demonstrated marked by enhanced DTH response and rise test percentage in neutrophil. Carbohydrates, glycosides, flavonoids, phenolic compounds is chemical compounds. Ethanol, methanolic, and aqueous extract are used to steam, flower, and leaf plants. It is used to treat *ABUTILON INDICUM* in order to improve immunological response, adaptive immune response, and resistance to diseases.

7.10. WOUND HEALING:

Steam, seeds, and aged root are used to prepare it. In particular, it is employed in methanolic and hexane extracts. It encourages cellular growth and repair by protecting tissues from oxidative damage. Ganga suresh et al assessed abutilon indicum linn's capacity to heal wounds. Rate of wound closure significantly increased analyse phytochemicals were perfumed on extracts. Track in wound margin day allowed monitoring alternation progressive.

7.11. DIURETIC ACTIVITY:

It was investigated whether a 70% hydroalcoholic extract abutilon indicum flower had diuretic effects. More doses (250 and 500mg/kg) extract demonstrate diuretic effects weaker than reference standard medication furosemide (200mg/kg). Methanolic extracts from fruits, plants, and other sources. Included are hematuria (blood in the urine), kidney stones, urinary infections, excessive urine output, electrolyte excretion, and the management of urinary issues.

7.12. ANTI-HYPER LIPID LOWERING ACTIVITY:

The entire plant is used, including the roots, seeds, and leaves. The leaf extracts utilized in water and ethanolic extracts in succession. High serum triglyceride levels, elevated HDL-Cholesterol levels, increased lipolysis, decreased adipocyte lipid accumulation, and hypercholesterolemia are all treated by its production in triglycerides, which inhibits the release of free fatty acids from adipose tissue and increases lipoprotein activity.

7.13. LARVICIDAL ACTIVITY:

The toxicity of crude hexane, ethylacetate, petroleum ether, acetone, and methanolic extracts of Abutilon indicum was tested for larvicidal efficacy. The petroleum ether extract of Abutilon indicum, Jatropha gossypifolia, Euphorbia thymifolia, and Solanum torvum was evaluated against *Culex quinquefasciatus* larvae in their early fourth instar. After a 24-hour exposure, the larval mortality was noted. Moderate larvicidal effects were shown by all extracts. *Abutilon indicum* leaves contained beta-sitosterol, which demonstrated larvicidal activity against mosquitoes.

7.14. ANTI-CONVULSANT ACTIVITY:

The current study findings showed that 100mg/kg extract significantly reduced tonic seizures overproduction in clonic convulsions. When

compared to the control group, ethanolic and aqueous extracts significantly reduced extensor time and increased the onset of clonic convulsion time. The extract's linoleic acid and/or flavonoid components were thought to be responsible for this anticonvulsant effect. PTZ (pentyleneterazole) extracts are made from whole plant parts. In ethanolic extracts, it caused seiryeres. Recurrent seizures, generalized psychonolor epilepsy, fertile epilepsy, and shortening the duration of tonic activity are all treated with this activity.

7.15. ANTI-ULCER ACTIVITY:

The ethanolic extract of *ABUTLION INDICUM*, especially its leaves, is most frequently used in studies on anti-ulcer efficacy. Studies have shown that it reduces gastric acid output, increases the formation of mucus, reduces peptic ulcers, and protects against ulcer-causing ageis, gastroesophageal problems, and duodenal ulcers. The purpose of study show how abutilon indicum can prevent ulcers in animals models. Aspirin pylorus induced by ligation models were used to test anti-ulcer activity. Outcomes were compared common medication famotidine .

7.16. ANTI-CANCER ACTIVITY:

Because of its anti-neoplastic qualities and ability to inhibit the proliferation of cancer cells, ethanolic and methanolic extracts of *ABUTLION INDICUM* are most commonly used.

Hodggkins lymphoma, breast cancer, colon cancer, ovarian cancer, lymphomas, Wilm's tumors, acute luckemius, neuroblastoma, endometrial cancer, lung cancer, prostatic cancer, carcinoma, Abutilon indicum and blumea mollis two medicinal plants, were selected for study order to check for possible cytotoxic action.

CONCULSION

This study highlights the taxonomy, Ayurvedic, Morphology, microscopy, Ethono claim uses, phytochemical constituents and pharmacogicals activites of the medicinal plant abutilon indicum has been belonging to the malvaceae family. *Abutilon indicum* [Thuthi] has been traditionally utilized in traditional medicine to treat a wide range of medical conditions. Traditional healers utilized forever part of this plant, as well as the leaves, flower, root, bark and seeds. The phytochemical studies show that *abutilon indicum* contains different natural compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, Tannins, glucosides, steroids, amino acids and phenolic compounds and physicochemical evaluation determined. These phytochemical were responsible for various Pharmacological activities including antimicrobial, antifungal, hepatoprotective, antiinflammatory, antidiabetic, antidiarrheal, antioxidant, immunomodulatory, wound healing, diuretic, antihyperlipids, larvicidal, anticonvulsant, anti ulcers, anticancer, analgesic etc., and it's high content minerals validate it's rich nutritional facts. Numerous in Pharmacological investigations have shown a connection between the conventional application of herbs in Thuthi supports the medicinal value. According to Pharmacological studies in this plant amounts and careful dose finding are required to confirm its safety. Overall this review on abutilon indicum emphasizes the therapeutic importance and submits that further experimental, analytic and harmonization studies are required to found its safety, efficacy and potential for improvement as a harmonization of herbal medicines.

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